

Useful ISWA Products For Europa Clipper Explained (+ Extra)

Prepared by *Yihua Zheng*
updated 17 July 2025

To: *Michael Kokorowski (JPL)*
Mission Assurance Manager

The WSA+ENLIL Model Suite

Wang-Sheeley-Arge (WSA Model)

1 Rs – 21.5Rs (0.0046 - 0.1AU)
 an empirical model predicting the background solar wind speed and interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) polarity

- 1 Rs ~ 2.5 Rs: PFSS (Potential Field Source Surface) Model of inner coronal magnetic field. Input: photospheric magnetic field maps (can be from satellite observations such as SOHO/MDI or SDO/HMI or ground-based observations such as the GONG magnetogram)
- 2.5 Rs ~ 5 Rs: the Schatten Current Sheet (CS) component
- 5 Rs – 21.5 Rs: the third and final component of the WSA model. Uses the field solution at 5 solar radii to generate a wind speed (empirical formula)

Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG) magnetogram

WSA: Utilizes synoptic map of the Sun's Photospheric magnetic field
 Generates global velocity and magnetic polarity map

- The solar wind forms a spiral.
- The Sun's magnetic field (black and white dotted lines) also follows this spiral.
- Charged particles travel along these field lines (circling them)

*WSA-ENLIL model:
Solar wind velocity contour plot in
the ecliptic plane*

The
WSA+ENLIL +
CME

Magnetic footpoint's relationship to the eruption site (longitude) matters!

the maximum values of peak intensity occur at values of ϕ close to about 0° or slightly negative (eruption site is to the east of the nominal spacecraft's footpoint)

$$\phi = \phi_{Flare} - \phi_{Foot.}$$

Lario, D., Kallenrode, M. -B., Decker, R. B., Roelof, E. C., Krimigis, S. M., Aran, A., & Sanahuja, B. (2006). Radial and Longitudinal Dependence of Solar 4–13 MeV and 27–37 MeV Proton Peak Intensities and Fluences: Helios and IMP 8 Observations. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 653(2), 1531–1544. <https://doi.org/10.1086/508982>

Dalla, S., Hutchinson, A., Hyndman, R. A., Kihara, K., Nitta, N. V., Rodríguez-García, L., Laitinen, T., Waterfall, C. O. G., & Brown, D. S. (2025). Detection asymmetry in solar energetic particle events. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 696, A12. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202453000>

This example is for CMEs occurred from May 30-31, 2025.

The CME (coronal mass ejection, billions tons of solar wind plasma being ejected from the Sun) headed towards the magenta direction, Mars and Clipper were not in the path of CME(s). But their magnetic footpoints were very close. The footpoints were close to the eruption site and likely received radiation effects from solar energetic particles (SEPs – associated with energetic solar eruptions). So WSA+ENLIL+CME simulations can be used as a proxy for SEP (radiation) monitoring. Clipper can use magnetically close assets (magnetic footpoints are close) for radiation/SEP monitoring (measurements from Mars mission for this example, can also check the nearby Lucy -- if radiation measurements are available).

Other background info regarding the plot.

WSA-ENLIL+Cone Model For 5.5 AU with Completion Time: 2025-05-31T16:24Z

Model Inputs:

[2025-05-30T06:38:00-CME-001](#) with [CME Analysis](#): Lon.=-24.0, Lat.=1.0,

Speed=502.0, HalfAngle=34.0, Time21.5=2025-05-30T13:28Z
[2025-05-30T12:53:00-CME-001](#) with [CME Analysis](#): Lon.=-22.0, Lat.=-26.0,
Speed=506.0, HalfAngle=26.0, Time21.5=2025-05-30T19:16Z
[2025-05-31T00:15:00-CME-001](#) with [CME Analysis](#): Lon.=-9.0, Lat.=8.0,
Speed=1302.0, HalfAngle=47.0, Time21.5=2025-05-31T02:32Z

Cygnet (Products) in the layout

The layout includes 5 'cygnets'. The left one at the first row and those in the middle row are basically from the same product group called 'Enlil CME and Ambient Gallery'. The '?' at the upper right corner of each cygnet provides more info of the graphic. The header of the cygnet provides different choices via different tabs at the very top (you can make selections using different drop-down menus).

Clipper layout

<https://iswa.ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov/IswaSystemWebApp/?layout=europaclipper&ago=0d>

Got a question from Michael.

How do I update the layout to the current day?

Response

For the CME simulation with the outer boundary at 5.5 AU, it is event-based and only run when there are significant CME(s) present, the time tag would be the most recent one.

The CME simulations with the outer boundary at 2.0 AU (this is the default) are run more frequently and their time tag may be more recent.

Each cygnet has three tags (modes) at the bottom left corner: the first two tags are for 'single image mode' and 'time range mode' (when you want to see dynamic changes over time — this feature does not make much sense for CME simulations since they are already dynamic. But good for the cygnet with a single image & static view) respectively, the third tab is 'auto update mode'.

To ensure all displays are the most up-to-date, I would click on the third tab (like a circle) first (auto refresh), then click on the leftmost tab to get to the 'single image mode', the calendar (with date and time) will appear.

An ISWA layout for Clipper

An example of the ISWA layouts potentially useful for Clipper operations (some of products will be updated with better features/further improvements).

1st cygnet at the top row

The leftmost button is good for viewing CME simulation

The outer boundary is set at 5.5 AU for this one

The arrows indicate the places for choices/info/certain functions

You can change time tag here

Five magenta arrows corresponds to 'mode', 'parameter', 'planet options', 'cut planes' and 'outer boundary' options.

Magnetic Footprint of Four Inner Planets and a few Selected Spacecraft

Clipper

Color-coded is the modeled radial magnetic flux

The more complex/intense region your asset is connected to, the likely chance of possible SEPs when it erupts

Look for regions of high flux values (dark blue or dark red)

9

the solar surface footprint location of the interplanetary magnetic field lines connecting the four inner planets and selected spacecraft as it evolves over a 5-day period

Density map

Same as Slide 8 but for density and the outer boundary at 2AU

The outer boundary at 2.0 AU

Magnetic Connectivity Solarscape Viewer (in Development)
SDO AIA Composite (211/193.17)

Settings

14135
14130
14132
14134
14125
14129
14128
14127

SDO/AIA - 211 2025/07/08 19:28:45
SDO/AIA - 193 2025/07/08 19:27:32
SDO/AIA - 171 2025/07/08 19:26:57

2025-07-08 19:53:18

Where 'SDO AIA Composite' is to see other background options

This product remains to be further developed

When a spacecraft or a place of interest is connected to the far-side of the sun. The circles are supposed to be in dashed (dotted) lines. The features were taken down due to found errors. But the active regions and their info are correct

The arrows are the places you can explore

You can click on Where 'SDO AIA Composite' is to see other background options

Other Useful Sites

- RadLab Portal (radiation measurements)
 - <https://visualization.osdr.nasa.gov/radlab/gui/overview/>
- WSA+ dashboard
 - <https://ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov/wsa-dashboard/>
- SO (Solar Orbiter) STIX
 - <https://datacenter.stix.i4ds.net/view/ql/lightcurves#>
Proxy for flares in the field view of Solar Orbiter

If Clipper is close (in terms of magnetic connectivity) to an asset where near realtime radiation measurements are available, use them 😊

Viewing orbit of different satellites/planetary bodies (provided by Peter Macneice)

<https://solar-mach.github.io/>

<https://eyes.nasa.gov/apps/solar-system/#/home>